

Civic Learning: Ethnographic Insights into How Pakistani Youth Construct Meanings of Global Citizenship

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Abstract

The current ethnographic research uses thick descriptions to analyse how Pakistani youth form meanings of global citizenship in schools. The research is based on six months of participant observation in three secondary schools in Punjab province and deployed detailed fieldnotes to capture the micro processes in which students engage in negotiating a variety of and sometimes competing identity positions national, religious, ethnic, and global. The analysis uses Geertz's interpretive framework to 98 fieldnote transcripts in classrooms, peer interactions, and informal interactions of youth, presenting their conceptualisations of global citizenship. The results show that global citizenship is created by Pakistani young people not in the form of wholesale appropriation of Western liberal forms but in the contextualised synthesis of a situation in which Islamic values, national loyalty, and selective cosmopolitan orientations collide. Students reveal advanced forms of agency when confronted with inconsistencies between the curriculum requirements of universal human rights and their experience of geopolitical marginalisation. This research methodologically makes the contribution of detailing ethnographic fieldnotes as a valid analytical methodology to the study of citizenship education and substantively theorising global citizenship as a localised, contentious, and culturally mediated practice among Pakistani youth.

INTRODUCTION

Global citizenship education (GCED) has become a prevailing paradigm of international education policy, advocated by UNESCO Sustainable Development Goal 4.7 and a part of national policy in countries such as Pakistan (Akkari & Maleq, 2020; Amin et al., 2023; Nasreen & Khushbakht, 2021). However, the attempt to translate GCED rhetoric into the everyday lives of young people living in postcolonial societies has received little scholarly attention, especially through approaches that privilege native meanings instead of imposed theoretical constructs. This study addresses this gap by examining the following question using ethnographic fieldnotes and a thick description: What meanings of global citizenship are created by Pakistani secondary school students in their daily educational experience?

Pakistan is an interesting country for analysing its construction of global citizenship, as it is positioned at the crossroads of Islamic identity, postcolonial nation-building, and the influences of modern globalisation (Khalid et al., 2022; Muhammad & Brett, 2015; Muhammad et al., 2019). The National Educational Policy 2017 incorporates the GCED language, the first of which is a major preparation for citizens to be knowledge-based and global-based, yet Islamic values and national cohesion are also portrayed as priorities (GOP, 2017). This produces an educational landscape in which young people must find ways to negotiate competing requirements; thus, the meaning-making processes of these individuals should be the focus of extensive ethnographic attention.

The role of traditional citizenship education studies has been characterised by the extensive use of surveys, interviews, and types of documents, which tend to impose predetermined categories on participants' experiences (Lall, 2008, 2009; Muhammad,

2019; Rauf & Muhammad, 2024). Conversely, ethnographic fieldnotes give the researcher the opportunity to record the situated, emergent, and contextual nature of how young people actually participate in citizenship in their daily interactions. Applying the concept of a thick description by Geertz (1973), the proposed study is a step further than the inadequate descriptions, which simply describe the behaviour of the youth by having detailed descriptions of their contextually rich interpretation of the symbolic meanings the youth attribute to global citizenship concepts. The research was guided by three specific questions.

How do Pakistani youth interpret and articulate global citizenship concepts in everyday school contexts?

What cultural resources do students draw on to develop their understanding of global citizenship?

How do youths manage tensions between local (national, religious, and ethnic) and global identity positions?

Theoretical Framework

Thick Description as Interpretive Methodology

The methodological basis of the present study is Geertz's (1973) articulation of the thick description, which argues that human behaviour should be interpreted in a complex set of cultural meanings instead of being perceived as observable facts. A thick description means that the researcher must record not only what occurred but also the layered meanings the actors give to actions, and that between a wink and a twitch, externally identical actions with such enormous different meanings exist. In addressing research on citizenship education, the significance of thick descriptions allows the researcher to observe the various possible implications of a statement made by a student in which they describe themselves as

Pakistani first, based on the interactional situation, use by their peers, and how they relate to the official curriculum.

This type of interpretation is consistent with constructionist epistemology which considers knowledge to be socially constructed as opposed to objective discovery (Lincoln, 1985). The thick description promotes the credibility of the research, as it provides readers with adequate contextual information on which to judge the validity and applicability of the research findings, coupled with leaving its audiences to define the degree to which they resonate with their personal contexts. The approach is specifically best adapted to research on citizenship construction in the sense that citizenship is performative itself; that is, it is formed and constructed around repetitive practices, as opposed to being a fixed identity (Butler, 2005).

Global Citizenship in Postcolonial Contexts

The concept of global citizenship education is often traced back to Western liberal democracies that focus on cosmopolitanism, universal human rights, and the unity of humanity (Heater, 2003, 2004; Oxley & Morris, 2013). However, critical scholars have stated that GCED may be a form of neocolonialism when it overlooks the experiences of citizenship in postcolonial countries characterised by economic dependency, political chaos, and imperial repressive experiences (de Oliveira Andreotti & De Souza, 2011). What Pakistani young people talk about in these terms is the negotiation of global citizenship under certain historical circumstances: A nation-state established with a focus on religious identity, endless geopolitical conflicts, economic restrictions that do not guarantee the real global movement, and an education system that is subject to numerous competing agendas: nationalist, religious, neoliberal, and

developmental

(Karim & Aman, 2024; Pasha, 2022; Shar, 2024).

Pakistani policymakers are also trying to maintain domestic cultural sensibilities, integrate global GCED models and regulatory bodies, develop hybrid policy documents, and cite both Islamic ethics and universal competencies. However, incorporating policies does not necessarily result in student uptake. Young people actively interpret, oppose, and reform official governmental discourses of citizenship based on their lived experiences, and this process must be explored in an ethnographic manner with indigenous categories and meanings (Emerson et al., 2011).

Youth as Active Meaning-Makers

The study considers youth not as passive recipients of citizenship lessons but as active individuals who can construct meaning through interaction. As explained in ethnomethodological approaches, it is believed that social order is achieved due to the everyday culture of sense-making by members, where people make use of culture repertoires to make sense of situations (Garfinkel, 2023). Pakistani youth have multiple concomitant identities; that is, they are simultaneously defined by their classes, gender, religion, ethnicity, and generation, which determine their interactions with global citizenship concepts (Rafiq et al., 2025; Safdar, Mahmood, Hameed, et al., 2025; Safdar, Mahmood, & Muhammad, 2025). Ethnographic fieldnotes are the most suitable for documenting the micro-level processes involved in the meaning provided to abstract concepts in specific situations.

Methodology

Research Design and Setting

The ethnographic research was conducted in three purposely chosen secondary schools in Pakistan, Punjab Province: one elite private

English-medium school, one government Urdu-medium school, and one semi-private school in a peri-urban area. This sampling method allowed us to analyse the impact of social status and educational background on global citizenship meaning making. The researcher played a participant-observer role and attended classes, followed by informal interactions with peers during breaks and even when taking part in extracurricular activities.

3.2 Data Collection Through Fieldnotes

In line with the systematic method of ethnographic fieldnotes (Emerson et al., 2011), there were three steps to data collection. First, jottings were recorded in place; in brief, phrases, keywords, and fragments were written during or immediately after observations. Second, these notes were developed into complete Fieldnotes in a matter of 24 hours and turned jottings into a narrative form of writing which recorded dialogue, physical location, emotional overtones, and first impressions by the researcher. Third, the use of asides and analytic memos was added to record the emergent themes, theoretical links, and reflexive notes regarding how the researcher positioned himself or herself.

Fieldnotes paid attention to those times when the element of global citizenship was explicitly or implicitly mentioned in times of discussions in the civics classroom, when students were together arguing about what happened in international events, when students were talking together about identity, and when students expressed feelings of belonging or not belonging in a less formal way. The researcher focused on the use of indigenous languages, where students were using English words as opposed to Urdu/Punjabi equivalents, and the interactional work of code-switching (Charmaz, 2006). In more than six months, 98 substantive fieldnote episodes were produced, amounting to approximately 250 pages of typewritten observation information.

Analytical Process

The analytical procedure was employed according to the iterative coding steps described by Emerson et al. (2011), considering analysis inseparable not only from the composition of fieldnotes per se but also from the stage that is separate in terms of time. The first themes were found using open coding when the Fieldnotes had been considered closely and recurring patterns, paying attention to common situations and the differences that indicated conceptual categories.

The next level of analysis focused on coding, followed by exploring the presence of these themes in other schools and students' groups regarding such variables as the grade level, gender, and the language of instruction. The researchers made their interpretation rigorous by including member checking where they exchanged Fieldnote snippets including rough interpretations with individual participants to verify accuracy and interpretative soundness. Analytic memos documented of an interpretation of how insight evolved with observation.

Ethical Considerations

The current research followed the general ethical standards of an ethnographic study carried out through the ethnographic fieldnotes. School administrators, parents, and student participants/participants received informed consent. Confidentiality was ensured using pseudonyms and by not disclosing the research sites. A reflexive concern of the researchers was the presence of power relationships in the research, especially in the face of adult youth and researchers' power imbalances (Trundle & Phillips, 2025).

Findings

Constructing Global Citizenship as Conditional Cosmopolitanism

The youth created global citizenship not by blindly following universalist values but by conditional cosmopolitanism—openness to world relationships within religious, national, and cultural specificities. This trend was observed in Fieldnote entries, which recorded discussions of international cooperation in classes. In one of the examples from the elite school in Lahore, when a discussion touched on human rights, a female student said, “We can cooperate with other nations, but we cannot adopt things that are contrary to Islam. It does not mean that global citizenship and identity make us lose ourselves” (Fieldnote 47). Her assertions illustrate how the negotiation between globalisation and identity maintenance proved to be very intricate, and this was the approach of many students.

This conditional position is manifested in different aspects of the classes. Elite school students with more realistic opportunities to travel internationally and study abroad have more cosmopolitan orientations and boundaries. One of the male students at the same school added, “I would love to work abroad and study abroad, but I will remain Pakistani in my heart. Global citizen does not mean no roots?” (Fieldnote 89). On the other hand, government school students explained global citizenship in aspirational frames that were not connected to any actual chances of mobile migration, showing how economic barriers influence citizenship imagination (Pasha, 2015).

The researchers noted that the official curriculum offering components of global citizenship as technical competence that was value-neutral caused the students to reject such framing, demanding foregrounding moral and religious aspects. This opposition implies that young agencies do not accept depoliticized neoliberal conceptions of global

citizenship as substantive ethical ideologies and principles based on Islamic social justice traditions and transnational solidarity.

Islamic Universalism as Alternative Global Framework

One impressive trend among fieldnotes was that students defined the phenomenon of Islamic identity as a type of global citizenship. The idea that the Ummah community of Muslims was in existence is what gave students an already extant framework to the conception of transnational belonging, which preceded and arguably competed with secular discourses of the GCED. In a lesson in a public school during social studies, the teacher asked the students to explain what global citizenship was, and several of them mentioned Ummah. Bilal, one of the students, elaborated and said, “Muslims are already global citizens. We have a single Ummah in each country. We assist Muslims worldwide.”

The Islamic cosmopolitan framing has several interactional functions. Originally, it enabled students to project global identity and retain religious authenticity to resolve potential contradictions between local and global, which burdened secular formulations. Second, it transformed Pakistani youth, who were treated as marginal recipients of Western GCED models, into carriers of a different, more tradition-grounded global culture. Third, it bridged the gap between the abstraction of citizenship concepts, and the practicability students were already familiar with, namely, charitable giving (Zakat), interest in fellow Muslims being oppressed around the world, and religious duties that did not respect specific nations.

However, tensions also manifest in Islamic universalism. Female students at the elite school observed that the use of Ummah rarely involved concerns of gender justice, and one of the female students stated, ‘They say that

Ummah is our international identity, but they do not pay attention to the treatment of women in certain Muslim nations. It is also a part of being global, because we are witnessing problems in our own community” (Fieldnote 91). These types of critical comments demonstrate that young people do not tend to embrace religious frameworks in the same way but instead apply them critically and display an advanced level of analytical abilities.

Performing Citizenship Through Code-Switching

Code-switching of language became one of the key practices, with the result that students practiced various citizenship identities in specific situations. Students at elite schools constantly changed between English and Urdu when expressing cosmopolitan global citizenship or true national belonging. According to fieldnotes, the pattern was the same most of the time: the conversation about international issues, technology, and professional ambitions proceeded in English, and the conversation about Pakistani identity, cultural values, and emotional belonging moved to either Urdu or Punjabi (Emerson et al., 2011).

This utterance was not merely instrumental alone but was part and parcel of citizenship. When this group entered one of the peer conversations (break time) to talk about recent international news, it was full of English, but as the subject changed towards what is being Pakistani, the group automatically shifted into Urdu. Subsequently, the researcher asked one of the students about this change. He pointed out, “English is about things of modernity and professional things. However, Urdu is our language. A similar thing happens when we discuss our emotions regarding Pakistan in English, which is not the same case” (Fieldnote 78). Language choice, therefore, marked identity territories, and code-switching were ways to find a connection

between global professional competence and national authenticity.

This was different from students in government schools, who had lower language fluency in English. In their case, mastering English was a sign of entry into world citizenship at the same time, indicating class exclusion. A student at one of the government schools complained that they were told that they were supposed to be global citizens and that without being able to communicate in English, they would not be able to compete with everyone. Global citizenship is associated with wealthy people. This fact shows the role of linguistic capital in the formation of unequal access to global citizenship identity, and it is crucial that the issue of equity is brought up through GCED programs.

Managing Contradictions Between Rights and Respect

An ongoing tension recorded in fieldnotes was that students negotiated between liberal rights-based citizenship and different modalities of culture, focusing on the themes of respect, hierarchy, and mandatory solidarity. This tension is often created explicitly in classroom discussions on human rights. In one civics lesson on basic rights in a peri-urban school, a case study was presented by the teacher concerning freedom of expression. Several of the students mentioned being out of place by one saying: “In Pakistan, we must respect elders and must respect religion. We cannot say all what we think. it is not our culture” (Fieldnote 12).

Instead of seeing this as a mere rejection of the rights discourse, it becomes clear through the thick description that negotiation is more complex. Students made hybrid formulations to settle competing paradigms. Various students differentiated between the categories of good rights (education, protection against harm, economic opportunity) and problem

rights (those that were viewed to weaken family, religious authority, and social cohesion). One student said: “Rights are good, but they are not so good that they kill society. The rights we require should be in line with our values” (Fieldnote 45). This culturally based rights discourse criticises global GCED models and simultaneously claims a valid right to dignity and justice (De Andreotti, 2006).

Females navigated this tension in a specially sophisticated manner. According to fieldnotes, there were many cases in which young women applied both rights and respect frameworks in a more or less strategic way, depending on circumstances and with whom they were talking. They applied the discourse of universal rights when discussing access to education and cultural respect values when discussing family relationships. This strategic code-switching was explicit in one female student, who said she discussed her right to education: “With my parents, I discuss how we need to respect their desires and how I simultaneously need to follow my dreams. Each of them is right, but you talk differently” (Fieldnote 21). This type of strategic competence is an indication of youth sophistication in their ability to handle various citizenship repertoires.

4.5 Experiencing Global Citizenship as Geopolitical Exclusion

One of the findings that was mostly not included in the official GCED literature and emphasised in fieldnotes was related to how the students experienced global citizenship in the context of Pakistan’s geopolitical marginalisation. Talks on the subject of international relations, barriers to visas, and worldwide attitudes towards Pakistan always lead to emotional manifestations of ineligibility to the global that cosmopolitan citizenship rhetoric assured. In one of the conversations about international study opportunities, several students mentioned frustration concerning visa challenges, and

one of them said:

“They are talking about global citizenship, but they do not want us in their own countries. We are suspected of having not yet applied” (Fieldnote 87).

This practical aspect influenced the students’ meaning of the global citizenship curriculum. Instead of absorbing global identity mindlessly, most students expressed what could be described as defensive cosmopolitanism: stating Pakistani superiority and contribution to world civilisation and denouncing Western hypocrisy. In a classroom lecture, one of the male students indicated in a conversation: “We invented algebra, preserved Greek philosophy, and raised great civilisations. Now, they look upon us as they think we are backwards. Global citizenship must also mean that they appreciate us” (Fieldnote 03). These utterances are indicative of the fact that colonial pasts and modern geopolitical inequalities define the meaning-making of citizenship in ways that are, in turn, overlooked by the elite systems of GCED (Andreotti, 2014).

Students also expressed awareness of the global citizenship competencies of English fluency, technological abilities, and cosmopolitan dispositions, which functioned as mechanisms for individual escape, rather than collective advancement. This tension was expressed by one of the female students with high academic performance: “I worked hard to be a global citizen, to leave Pakistan maybe. However, it feels like a betrayal. Does global citizenship mean being unfaithful to a country?” (Fieldnote 34). Her question sheds light on the ethical issues that GCED brings up among young people who lack funds in economically deprived settings when the notion of global citizenship is linked to the concept of brain drain instead of unity.

Silence and Performance in Formal Curriculum

Classroom interaction was described as thick, and significant gaps were found between students on the privacy of citizenship and formality when they were offered a chance to perform such roles in formal assessment settings. A similar pattern was observed in fieldnotes: in informal peer conversations and during one-on-one communication with the individual researcher, students showed sophisticated and critical views on global citizenship, whereas in the formal classroom, especially during an examination, students were rephrasing the official curriculum language using little or no critical thinking.

The eye-opening moment was when the researcher noticed that the same student, Zainab, was engaged in two different situations on the same day. She created a traditional essay on global citizenship with a focus on cooperation, peace, and universal values during the morning civic-class examination. At one afternoon break, she wrote to companions: "I wrote what you wanted to hear. However, in truth, the idea of global citizenship is another form of saying be like the West" (Fieldnote 98). This performance evidences the difference between official and indigenous meanings Emerson et al. (2011) in that students are aware of how to work out official discourse and maintain personal interpretive paradigms.

These strategic performances pose severe methodological concerns regarding research on citizenship education based on formal assessments or structured interviews, as these methods might only measure performed knowledge that does not reflect real meaning-making. Ethnographic fieldnotes bring such indigenous meanings that are ignored by standardised methodologies because they capture the informal contexts in which students feel less inhibited in articulating their positions (Charmaz, 2006).

Discussion

Theoretical Contributions

This study contributes to the existing knowledge on global citizenship education in three important ways. First, it shows that young people in postcolonial societies do not passively embrace or resist the GCED frameworks but pass through complex processes of cultural synthesis by making hybrid citizenship identities that simultaneously use and rely on numerous, and often competing, systems of meaning. The conditional cosmopolitanism of Pakistani students is a non-wholesale adoption of Western liberal modes and non-reactionary rejection, but an act of creative bricolage that develops practical identities informed by available cultural resources (Oxley & Morris, 2013).

Second, the results support the idea of universalising tendencies in GCED scholarship because they shed light on the significant influence of geopolitical positioning, economic constraints, and colonial legacies on the construction of citizenship. The defensive cosmopolitanism described here, the youth claiming to contribute to civilisation and critiquing Western hypocrisy, are experiential realities of marginalisation that are whitewashed by the rhetoric of the GCED. This implies that transformative citizenship education should clearly respond to power disparities and not advance decontextualised global peace discourse (De Andreotti, 2006).

Third, this paper postulates citizenship as a performative achievement that entails identity work that is situation specific. The language code-switching and strategic application of rights versus respect paradigms by students, as well as their variances in performance in formal and informal forms, demonstrate citizenship not as an identity, but as a practice that is occurring and situated. Such processual understanding opposes the essentialist

assumptions that frequently lie in citizenship education policies (Butler, 2005).

Methodological Contributions

Methodologically, this paper shows how ethnographic fieldnotes have the unique ability to record indigenous meanings and micro-level processes that are otherwise opaque to other methods of research. This rich description allowed us to note some finer aspects of interaction, such as pauses, tone shifts, the use of other languages, contradictions in formal and informal speech, and how citizenship is constructed in everyday life. Questionnaires on attitudes towards citizenship would fail to capture the sophisticated strategy of performing official discourse while maintaining private critical perspectives. Even interviews, during which formal relations between researchers and participants are manifested, may fail to elicit spontaneous discussions under which we can see authentic meaning-making (Emerson et al., 2011).

It has also been discussed how analytic benefits can be achieved by viewing fieldnote writing as analytical work, as opposed to data collection. The iterative process of moving between observations, jottings, full Fieldnotes, and analytic claims based on groups of participants and the areas of their concern allowed the development of emergent themes. Instead of theoretical approaches imposed on students, indigenous ideas emerged due to the actual language of students, making ecological concepts more valid (Charmaz, 2006).

However, this methodology has some limitations. The contextual richness of a thick description is its strength, which limits its generalisability in conventional meanings. The results are not statistically representative but have theoretical transferability; that is, they present ideas and models that may be used in similar conditions. In addition, the researcher's presence is bound to influence

observed

interactions, even though reactivity anxieties are partly addressed by the length of engagement and the technique of member checking (Lincoln, 1985).

Implications for Citizenship Education Policy and Practice

These results have implications for citizenship education policies and pedagogy. First, curriculum developers should be aware that students are already aware of models of global belonging to religious identity, cultural values, historical consciousness, and so on that cannot be ignored or overwritten. The fact that cosmopolitan citizenship is a potential outcome of effective GCED entails the necessity to involve these frameworks directly and not to emphasise the aspect of cosmopolitan citizenship as a culturally neutral technical competence.

Second, teachers must provide time and space in which children can express and resolve contradictions instead of forcing them to do so. The conflicts recorded here, one between local and global, rights and respect, and aspiration and exclusion, are fruitful locations of critical thinking and not issues to be eradicated. More complex pedagogies can now support students' actual sense-making processes.

Third, citizenship education should be concerned with the structural inequalities which determine unequal opportunities for global citizenship identity. The observed relations between English fluency, class status, and perceived rights as world citizens indicate how GCED can reinforce privilege without clear intentions to use it unless equity commitments are implemented. This makes it possible to believe that the citizenship curriculum should include language policy, economic assistance to marginalised students, and a critical reflection of power relations in the world (Pasha, 2025).

Conclusion

Ethnographic research has used the thick description approach to explore Pakistani youth formulations of global citizenship and has found intricate mechanisms of cultural synthesis, strategic acting, and critical engagement with competing identity pressures. The study reported multiple episodes of fieldnotes through an extensive examination of patterns of conditional cosmopolitanism, Islamic universalism as alternative global formations, linguistic code-switching as citizenship performance, the balance of rights and respect, bodily knowledge of geopolitical exclusion, and the strategic distinction between formal and informal articulations of citizenship.

The results show that Pakistani youth are not passive receivers of the GCED curriculum but sophisticated interpreters and are still constructing viable identities by using diverse cultural materials. Their meaning-making practices show global citizenship to be disputed, contextual, and culturally situated. Ethnographically, in a methodological way, the research depicts the rare ability of ethnographic fieldnotes to elicit indigenous meanings and micro-processes not reflected in other research methods, which contends that researchers should apply thick descriptions in the study of citizenship education.

This study adds to the current discussion of culturally responsive pedagogy, postcolonial approaches to international education models, and the application of qualitative methodology to the study of lived experiences of policy implementation. The current study can be broadened by further research in national contexts. How teachers cope with such tensions themselves should be studied, and how youth citizenship as a concept can be transformed by entering adulthood. Moreover, comparative ethnographic analyses to investigate GCED meaning making in other postcolonial settings might help to clarify what patterns observed in this country are

specific to Pakistan

and which to the specific postcolonial dilemmas.

The main finding of the thick description is that global citizenship cannot be generalised and forced but should be recognised as a world created locally, relying on cultural possibilities and reacting to living realities which differ dramatically in various global situations. Embracing such diversity is not the failure of universal GCED frameworks, but rather a chance to create more viable, culturally grounded strategies of equipping young people to live in a globalised but deeply unequal world. The sophisticated political negotiations of citizenship identity clearly expressed by Pakistani young people also provide important lessons to teachers, policymakers, and researchers interested in citizenship education, that honours rather than erases cultural difference while still fostering critical global consciousness.

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